

A NOTE ON THE OXIDATION OF RED PHOSPHORUS BY POTASSIUM CHLORATE

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The qualitative aspect of the oxidation of phosphorus by potassium chlorate has been studied by many workers (Bottger, *Rep. Pharm.*, 1875, 24, 725; Slater, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1853, i, 60, 274; Schrotter, *Sitzber. Akad. Wien*, 1848, 1, 130) who have shown that phosphorus and phosphoric acids are formed as the end products. During studies in these laboratories on the quantitative aspect of the above oxidation process, their reactions were found to be rather complicated, and conditions determining the reaction in some particular phase were studied.

The decomposition of KClO_3 as $\text{KClO}_3 \rightarrow \text{KCl} + 3\text{O}$ and the utility of the three atoms of oxygen for the oxidation of P to phosphoric acid have been studied in solutions containing sulphuric acid of 1N (overall N being $\left\langle 1\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4 \right\rangle$). The reaction is represented by

Thus, it was found that 6 molecules of P would require 5 of KClO_3 for quantitative oxidation on the basis of the above reaction. Apart from these considerations, complete and quantitative oxidation was invariably impracticable; but from the results, the percentage of oxidation could be evaluated.

Procedure.—A known quantity of pure dry red P was weighed into a Kjeldhal flask provided with a Liebig condenser attached with a ground glass seal. About 5 to 10 times (the weight of P taken) pure Merck's sample of potassium chlorate was tapped into the flask and 40 c.c. of $\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was added and the whole system refluxed for about 6 to 8 hours by direct heating. On completion of the reaction, the flask was cooled and the remaining solution of excess chlorate made up to 250 c.c., 50 c.c. of which was pipetted into a conical flask and an excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (50 c.c. of $\text{N}/10$) was added to it, followed by dilute H_2SO_4 . The flask was fitted up with a cork provided with a Bunsen type of valve tube and the contents boiled. It was cooled and the excess ferrous sulphate titrated against KMnO_4 solution.

The above experiments were repeated in the presence of a catalyst, viz., manganous sulphate. To the contents in the flask about 5, 10, 15 and 20 c.c. of an 1% solution of Merck's manganous sulphate was added prior to refluxing, and experiments carried out. A few of the results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Overall acidity $\llcorner$ 1N-H₂SO₄.

P taken.	KClO ₃ .	Catalyst (1% MnSO ₄).	Unchanged KClO ₃ .	Changed KClO ₃ .	P (calc.).	Diff.
0.0212 g.	0.2720 g.	...	0.2046 g.	0.0674 g.	0.02047 g.	0.00073 g.
0.0336	0.2720	...	0.1741	0.0979	0.02971	0.00389
0.0338	0.2958	...	0.1941	0.1017	0.03085	0.00295
0.0132	0.2958	5 c. c.	0.2532	0.0426	0.01293	0.00027
0.0400	0.2958	10	0.1751	0.1207	0.03662	0.00338
0.0426	0.2958	15	0.1680	0.1278	0.03877	0.00383
0.0290	0.2958	20	0.2053	0.0905	0.02746	0.00154

The results show the erratic behaviour of the oxidant in the reaction. Also the results obtained by back-titration of chlorate were slightly variable from that obtained by titrating the chloride formed in solution by the Volhard method.

Accuracy of the method has been found to vary from 2 to 10% negative error, for P ranging from 0.02 to 0.04 g. and hence 90% of red P goes to complete oxidation. Manganous sulphate catalysed the reaction to some extent, for it was observed that more of P was oxidised to phosphoric acid in the same time.

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